

AUTONOMOUS ENERGY EFFICIENCY WITH HYBRID PANEL

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Summary. One of the important factors that negatively affects the efficiency of solar panels is temperature. To prevent efficiency loss, liquid cooling or air cooling methods are used. Since air cooling has disadvantages, liquid cooling is more profitable. While the efficiency of the panel is balanced by liquid cooling, the efficiency is increased by using the heated liquid in various ways. A case study was conducted using the heated liquid in the prototype to heat the greenhouse. When both electrical and thermal energy are provided through a single system, the efficiency of the system is increased and the photovoltaic system is more stable. In our study, Arduino-based software was used to control the system. Instantaneous electrical data generated by the panel and sensors in the prototype were observed and controlled through an LCD screen. The electrical energy obtained from the panels was first collected in batteries, and the energy was later usable. Excess energy that could not be stored in the batteries was pumped into the irrigation tanks integrated into the greenhouse prototype, ensuring more efficient use of energy.

Keywords: Greenhouse, solar panel, remote control, energy efficiency.

1. INTRODUCTION

The energy requirement of the growing population and developing industry is increasing rapidly, and this energy requirement cannot be met with the current limited resources (Kandilli et al., 2013). Energy has become indispensable for the developing world and our lives. The vast majority of the energy we consume is fossil fuels, nuclear energy and renewable energy sources. The high costs of energy production have enabled the spread of efficient and sustainable energy sources. PVT systems, which aim to use heat energy as well as electricity in photovoltaic (PV) systems, have been studied since the 1970s. These systems are based on the use of PV and thermal systems together. In the literature, there are many studies on the design, thermodynamic analysis and performance evaluation of PVT systems (Tripanagnostopoulos, 2017) (Hendrie, 1979). The aim of this study is to reduce the effect of temperature, which negatively affects efficiency in PV panels. The efficiency increase is aimed by reducing the temperature effect with the designed PV-T system.

With this designed system, electricity and heat energy are produced simultaneously. The heat energy obtained from the PV-T system can be used as heating or hot water in homes and workplaces (Duran, 2014).

Figure 1. Graphs of the effect of operating temperature on the PV panel

PV-T systems can be in 3 different forms;

1. Liquid type flat PV/T collectors: In this type of PV/T systems, water or the fluid used is circulated in the collector plate and heat is collected. In case of hot water demand, it is an advantage to use this type of system.

2. Air type flat - PV/T collectors: In air type flat PV/T collectors, air is circulated instead of liquid fluid in the collector to heat the air. These types of collectors should be used in areas where heated air is needed

3. Concentrated PV/T collectors: In concentrated PV/T collectors, sun rays are collected and reflected to a central point where the PV/T module is located (Koç and Başaran, 2019).

In this study, a liquid type flat PV-T collector system was created. This system is a preferred system in case of hot water demand. It is important that the area where the system will be installed has a flat structure. The hot water obtained from the system is stored in hot water tanks. The disadvantage of storage is freezing in winter months, leakage in the long term and calcification in fog channels. Electrical efficiency is higher in liquid type PV-T Systems. The most important reason for this is the high heat losses in PV-T systems.

The electricity and heat energy produced in the study was used in the designed greenhouse prototype. In the greenhouse prototype in the project, the optimum conditions required for a plant to grow are controlled by a sensor network. A system that can make real-time measurements using the sensor network, store data, provide suitable conditions for the product to be grown according to the data it receives, present this data to the user's observation, and authorize the user to intervene has been created. The control of the sensor network can be controlled manually from the control panel in the prototype and remotely with a mobile application.

2.MATERIAL AND METHOD

In the prototype of the project, polycrystalline solar panel, inverter, battery charge controller, battery, arduino uno, arduino mega, arduino lcd screen, soil moisture sensor, water level sensor, gas sensor, temperature-humidity sensor, rain sensor, I_{dr} , submersible water pump, motor driver circuit, fan and lighting led were used. The polycrystalline solar panel in the system was adapted to the hybrid panel operating principle that produces hot water (heat) and electrical energy. Cooling pipes were placed at the back of the polycrystalline solar panel used, turning the panel into a hybrid panel. Thus, the new panel converted into a hybrid panel reduced the temperature and cooled the panel. In PV-T Systems, heat energy is obtained while cooling the panel.

They designed a new type of PVT where copper pipe and functionally graded material (FDM) were used behind the PV panel, they modeled the PVT design they developed both experimentally in a laboratory environment and with the finite element method (FEM) and compared the findings. They concluded that the simulation results they obtained were compatible with the experimental results (Yang et al., 2012). Copper was selected as the type of material to be used behind the panel for cooling the PV Module (Kandilli, 2017).

Table 1.
Electrical conductivity and thermal conductivity of some materials (Internet, 2019).

Metal	Electrical Conductivity (mega – Siemens/m)	Thermal Conductivity (W /Mk)
Silver (Ag)	62	408
Copper (Cu)	55	388
Gold (Au)	45	309
Aluminum (Al)	33	203

In this system, the type of liquid channels is important to achieve optimum heat efficiency. When the type of materials is examined based on electrical conductivity and thermal conductivity,

the most efficient material is silver. Copper, gold, and aluminum come in order. Since silver and gold are expensive in terms of cost, they are not preferred. Therefore, it is appropriate to prefer copper based on cost and efficiency. In the project, hot water from the PV-T system enters the system designed for space heating. The water that transfers energy is stored in the cold water tank. The stored water is sent back to the panel and circulation is provided. The reason for establishing such a system is that the water constantly drawn from the network will cause calcification and will not cause calcification again since the same water will be used in subsequent circulations. Thus, efficiency was increased.

Figure 2. General view of the prototype

The electrical energy obtained from the solar panel was stored in the battery with the charge control device. The stored energy was converted to 220V AC with the help of the inverter. The electricity need of the greenhouse was met with this converted energy. Thus, a system independent of the network was established and energy efficiency was achieved. The light intensity falling on the panel was measured with the light intensity sensor ldr. The measured data was printed to the serial port screen via Arduino Uno. In addition, the light intensity was observed instantly as low and high light levels via LEDs with the LDR card we designed. The automation part of the system was completed with 7 sensors, 1 LCD screen, 1 submersible pump, 1 motor driver, fan and lighting LED to automate the greenhouse system. The rainfall status of the weather was controlled with the rain sensor we used. The greenhouse roof was designed to be opened and closed according to the rain. It was made easier to take precautions to prevent damage to the products to be grown in greenhouses with openable roofs from rain. The temperature-humidity sensor obtains measurement data to keep the temperature and humidity of the greenhouse at the ideal level. The temperature-humidity ratio was kept at the optimum level with the fans placed on the roof. The soil moisture status was monitored with the soil moisture sensor.

The data received from this sensor provided the opportunity to water the plants at the correct intervals. The irrigation system was made with the help of the motor driver and submersible pump used. The motor driver operates the submersible pump according to the data from the soil moisture sensor and the irrigation job is carried out. Thus, it ensures that the plants are watered at the right time. The water level in the greenhouse tank was checked with the water level sensor. If the water level is low, it was communicated to the user that irrigation will not be done and the engine will not work to prevent technical problems. In general, the data received from the temperature-humidity sensor, rain sensor, water level sensor and soil moisture sensor were provided with information on the LCD screen. Thus, the necessary information was provided to the user. By measuring the carbon dioxide level of the environment with the gas sensor, early warning information was given with the designed notification system in case the carbon dioxide level in the greenhouse increased. System control was provided with Arduino-based software. Instant electrical data generated from the panel was monitored on the LCD screen.

Alternatively, data control was made via the mobile application. With this project, the temperature that negatively affected the efficiency of the solar panel was eliminated and efficient

electrical energy was obtained. A controllable system that provides suitable growing conditions for plants was created with greenhouse automation. The necessary information was provided to the user with the created system, and convenience was provided.

3. CONCLUSION

In the prototype test studies, the PV/T system fixed on the prototype was interpreted by taking the Düzce province Konuralp region as reference, without changing the location, taking into account the 5-month produced energy, wind speed, and sunshine duration.

Figure 3. Average sunshine duration (Hours)

In Figure 3, the average hours of sunshine between December and April are given in the graph. Starting from January, sunshine duration has shown an approximately linear increase. The increase in sunshine duration has directly affected the increase in electricity production.

Figure 4. Average wind speed (Km/h)

In Figure 4, when the wind speed was examined in a 5-month period, it was effective at 12 km/h. While the presence of wind positively affected the production of electrical energy, it negatively affected the production of hot liquid. The heating planned to be obtained from the PV/T system in the winter months could not be met with the hot liquid. This situation caused a disadvantage. Cooling

with liquid could not provide the expected efficiency on the prototype in the winter months. It was predicted that the system could not meet the expectation in greenhouse farming in the Düzce region. It is predicted that the system efficiency will increase and its applicability will be in the greenhouse activities carried out in the Mediterranean and Aegean regions. In Düzce province, the PV/T system can be preferred not for heating purposes but for usable hot water.

In our project, instead of the liquid type flat-PV/T collectors, air type flat PV/T collectors were used. They are less costly than liquid type flat PV-T collectors and have more advantages since there is no risk of freezing, boiling or damage to the system in case of leakage. However, air type PV/T collectors have some major disadvantages such as having lower thermal performance compared to liquid type PV/T collectors. Since the circulation fluid has a low heat capacity, it has lower heat transfer. Therefore, it is not suitable for low volume applications and larger volume pipes that are not aesthetically pleasing are required in the installation. The priority in the project is not to make large PV/T systems, but to create a system that can be used in daily life and is accessible to everyone.

REFERENCES

1. DURAN, F. (2014), Thermodynamic and performance analysis of PV/T hybrid systems, 03 May 2019, <http://tez.sdu.edu.tr/Tezler/TF02586.pdf>.
2. <http://diyot.net/metallerin-iletkenlik-ve-diger-ozellikleri/>, 03 May 2019 .
3. Hendrie, S.D. (1979), 'Evaluation of combined Photovoltaic/Thermal collectors. In: Proceedings of International Conference ISES', Atlanta, Georgia, USA, May 28 – June 1, vol. 3, pp. 1865–1869.
4. KANDİLLİ, C. (2017), Investigation of thermodynamic and economic performance of photovoltaic thermal systems (PVT) integrated with phase change materials, 03 April 2019, <http://mmoteskon.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/05/2017-086.pdf> .
5. KANDİLLİ, C. and KÜLAHLI, G. and SAVCI, G. (2013), Photovoltaic Thermal (PVT) System 2D thermodynamic modeling and comparison with experimental results, 03 May 2019, <http://mmoteskon.org/wp-content/uploads/2014/09/2013-83.pdf>.
6. KINCAY, O. and BEKİROĞLU, N. and YUMURTACI, Z. (2019), Solar Cells (Photovoltaic Cells), Retrieved on April 20, 2019 from <http://www.yildiz.edu.tr/~okincay/dersnotu/gunespilleri1bolum.pdf>.
7. KOC, I. and BASARAN, K. (2019), Performance analysis of a PV/T based system using MATLAB/Simulink, Retrieved on April 23, 2019 from <http://dergipark.gov.tr/politeknik/archive>.
8. Tripanagnostopoulos, Y. (2017), 'Aspects and improvements of hybrid photovoltaic/thermal solar energy systems', Solar Energy 81 1117–1131.
9. Yang DJ, Yuan Z.F., Lee P.H., Yin H.M. (2012), 'Simulation and experimental validation of heat transfer in a novel hybrid solar panel', Heat and Mass Transfer 55 1076-1082.